

The Influence Of Traditional Arts In Improving The Economy Of Traditional Performers Of Performing Arts Sandur Bojonegoro, Indonesia

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Abstract: This study aims to determine the influence of traditional arts, namely the art of sandur performance on the income of creative economic actors. Creative economy actors here are the parties involved in the art of sandur performance. The research location is in the village of Ledok Kulon, Bojonegoro by taking samples of the members of the sandur performing arts group. The method used in this research is quantitative by using statistical techniques of simple linear regression analysis. The hypothesis test used in this study is the statistical test. The data used is primary data, namely data obtained directly by conducting interviews and distributing questionnaires or questionnaires to the parties involved in the art of sandur performance.

keywords: influence, sandur performing arts, creative economy actors

I. INTRODUCTION

Reducing unemployment, poverty or inequality is a success in economic development. Economic life below the poverty line and the number of unemployed illustrate that economic development has not been successful. According to the Central Statistics Agency and the Creative Economy Agency, the creative industry or what is known as the creative economy is one of the strategic sectors that makes a significant contribution to the Indonesian economy. This industry, which was born from individual creativity, then again gives birth to many new job opportunities and improves the welfare of the surrounding community. The Gross Domestic Product (GDP) of the creative economy obtained in 2016 was 922.59 trillion rupiah. (greatday, 2020)

The creative industry plays an important role in the national and global economy because it contributes to aspects of life both economically and non-economically. The hope is that the creative economy will be developed in order to build the economy. An important goal in economic development is to provide sufficient employment opportunities to pursue labor force growth, especially for developing countries such as Indonesia where the growth of the labor force is faster than the growth of employment opportunities. (Wahyu Saputro, 2018: 2).

Performing arts is one of the sixteen creative economy sub-sectors identified by the Ministry of Tourism and Creative Economy that involve several creative skills. Performing arts creative industries are creative activities related to: content development, performance production, ballet performances, traditional dances, contemporary dances, dramas, traditional music, music-theatre, opera, including ethnic music tours, design and manufacture of performance clothing, hairdressing stage, and lighting. (Sri Rachmayanti, 2019)

Performing arts which are included in the creative industry sub-sector cannot be separated from the traditional arts of an area that have been created into something worthy of being staged. Indonesia has arts in

each region, one of which is Bojonegoro Regency. Bojonegoro Regency itself has several kinds of performing arts including Puppet Thengul, Wayag Krucil, Tayub and Sandur.

The performing art "Sandur" has become an icon of Bojonegoro Regency. Sandur himself is no stranger to the people of Bojonegoro. During the sandur performance, the people of Bojonegoro were enthusiastic in watching because the story process was unique and fun. Achmad Ilham Muji Prasetya (in Sandur Art and Identity Bojonegoro 05 October 2019).

The existence of sandur had experienced suspended animation because it was believed that sandur was a communist culture during the colonial period. Sandur is a combination of several types of arts including theatre, dance, music, and visual arts. In combining the arts, there are various kinds of needs that are needed to support the success of a performance. For this reason, sub-sectors of the performing arts industry are needed, such as directors, actors, choreographers, scriptwriters, artistic stylists, lighting stylists, sound stylists and fashion and make-up stylists.

Based on the explanation above, the authors are interested in conducting research with the title "The Influence of Traditional Arts in Improving the Economy of Traditional Performers of Sandur Bojonegoro Performing Arts".

II. METHODS

This research uses descriptive research with survey method. According to Sugiyono (2012: 29) descriptive method is a method used to describe or analyze a research result but is not used to make broader conclusions. The survey research method says that survey research is "research that takes a sample from a population and uses a questionnaire as the main data collection tool".

The scope of this research is the group of sandur art performers, and the focus of the research is the influence of the performing arts they run with the income they earn. The independent variable (X) in this study is the art of sandur performance with the dependent variable (Y) the income of creative economy actors. Variables were measured using a Likert scale to measure attitudes, opinions, and perceptions of a person or group of people about social phenomena. In research, this social phenomenon has been specifically determined by researchers, hereinafter referred to as research variables. (Sugiyono, 2009:132).

The assessment is carried out based on 1-5 by determining the conventional scale scoring score. Each instrument item that uses a Likert scale has a gradation from very positive to very negative, namely strongly agree with a score of 5, agree with a score of 4, in doubt a score of 3, disagree with a score of 2 and strongly disagree with a score of 1.

The research was conducted in one period, namely in 2020, the type of data used in this study was cross section. Cross section is data that shows research at the same time with different locations such as the rice harvest in 2000 in Medan, Balikpapan, Gorontalo and Lampung (esty setyaningrum, saptuyningsih, 2020: 86).

Data collection techniques used are primary and secondary data. The sample in this study used a non-probability sampling technique with a saturated sampling technique. Saturated sampling is a sampling technique when all members of the population are used as samples (Sugiyono, 2009:122). The sample in this study used the entire population of 40 people, namely all members of the sandur performing arts consisting of directors, music stylists, dance stylists, actors, dancers, musicians, production team, videographers, photographers, Make-Up Artists (MUA), artistic stylist, and assistant to MUA.

The location in this study is in Bojonegoro district, precisely in Ledok Kulon village, Bojonegoro sub-district at the Sanggar Wing Jendela Art laboratory in the Sandur Kembang Desa art group.

In this study, there is only one independent variable (X) namely sandur performances and one dependent variable (Y) namely the income of creative economy actors, so the researcher will use simple linear regression.

The equations of simple linear regression are as follows:

$$Y = a + bX$$

With information:

Y = subject in the predicted dependent variable (earnings of sandur actors)

a = constant (value of Y, if X=0)

b = regression coefficient (increase or decrease value) variable X

X = subject to the independent variable that has a certain value (performing Arts)

III. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Based on the results of simple linear regression analysis, it can be seen the relationship between the independent variable and the dependent variable. The equations used are:

$$Y = a + bX$$

With information:

Y = subject in the predicted dependent variable (earnings of sandur actors)

a = constant (value of Y, if X=0)

b = regression coefficient (increase or decrease value) variable X

X = subject to the independent variable that has a certain value (performing Arts)

Table 1
Simple Linear Regression Analysis Results (coefficients table)

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	2.125	1,928		1,102	,277
	Sandur Performing Arts (X)	,514	,123	,563	4,198	,000

a. Dependent Variable: Income Of Creative Economics (Y)

Sources: Primary Data processed

From the coefficient table, it can be seen that the constant value (a) is 2.125, while the value of Sandur performing arts (b / regression coefficient) is 0.514. So that the regression equation can be written:

$$Y = a + bX$$

$$Y = 2.125 + 0.514X$$

The constant of 2.215 means that the consistent value of the income variable is 2.125. The X regression coefficient of 0.514 states that for every 1% addition to the value of performing arts, the income value of creative economy actors increases by 0.514. The regression coefficient is positive, so it can be said that the direction of the influence of the variable X on Y is positive. Based on the significance value of the coefficients table obtained a significance value of 0.000 < 0.05. So it can be concluded that the performing arts variable (X) has an effect on the income variable of creative economic actors (Y).

Table 2
Hypothesis Test Results

Coefficientsa						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	2.125	1,928		1,102	,277
	Sandur Performing Arts (X)	,514	,123	,563	4,198	,000

a. Dependent Variable: Income Of Creative Economics (Y)

Sources: Primary Data processed

Based on the coefficients table, it is known that the t_{count} value is 4.198, while the t-table value based on the t_{table} (attached) on degrees of freedom df 38 and a significance level of 0.05 (5%) of 0.683. Then the value of t_{count} (4.198) > t_{table} (0.683) it can be concluded that H_a is accepted and H_o is rejected, which means that the sandur performing arts variable (X) has a partial effect on the income variable of economic actors (Y).

IV. CONCLUSIONS

The results of the simple linear regression analysis in this study show that the performing arts variable (X) affects the income variable of creative economic actors (Y) by 31.7% and every 1% increase in the performing arts variable (X) makes the coefficient value of the creative economy actor income variable (Y) increases by 0.514 and has a positive value. In the results of the partial test (t statistical test) it can be concluded that performing arts (X) have a partial effect on the income variable of creative economic actors (Y)

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